

A review on the Green Human Resources Management

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Abstract: A couple of years ago the employee's sustainability and green environment have increased. Corporations have diversified from normal environments to sustainable environments. This study aims to research Green human resources practices and employees' perceived sustainability on economic performance in OPET Corporation located in Istanbul Turkey. GHRM and sustainability are not been widely discussed well properly in past studies. Four independent variables GRS, GTP, GPR & GI, and one dependent variable EPS are proposed for this study. A simple random sampling method has been used with a 250 sample size. A Survey has conducted via questionnaires from 1st February 2022- to 1st May 2022 in Turkey. The data analysis in SPSS 27.0 Version.

Keywords: Green Human Resources Management, Green Training, Green Pay, Green Recruitment, Green Involvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

The intensifying worries of the worldwide surroundings have required various organizational exercises to itemize environmental matters and business sustainability (Ullah, 2017). Green management is swiftly evolving as a management paradigm for improving organizational competitiveness (Rawashdeh, 2018; Mishra et al., 2016). Especially in the Turkish Manufacturing area, where many industries adopt this managerial strategy in order to have an effective set of Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices which help the organizations to stay sustainable. (Lado & Wilson, 1994) elaborated the HRM system as “a collection of interrelated but distinguishable actions, operations, and procedures that are aimed to enticing, retaining (or disposing of) and advancing human resources of an organization”. In this study, greening will be the main topic, and as a result, a combination between this word “greening” and the (HRM) practices will be prevailed. It has been accepted that the green management practices help corporations to mimic the first-rate practices around the arena and even with the intention to be more adaptive and flexible to the surroundings environment. The applicability of these circumventing parts in its primary form is recognized by (Ullah, 2017) as “green”. In this regard, keep in mind that going green no longer means that an environment should be painted green, but that organizations operating in a commercial business location have taken measures to show they are conscious of their environment. (Kapil, 2015; Jabbour, 2011; Rani & Mishra, 2014) Nevertheless, the focal point of integrating environmental control into HRM practices is what researchers (Aburahma et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2020; Dutta, 2012) referred to as ‘green’ HRM. In addition, the various business practitioners, almost all the global enterprises nowadays have extremely sped up in greening the global business environments (O’Rourke, et al., 2016).

Environmental management systems should be recognized among the many tools developed to encourage environmental management in businesses. The ISO 14001 certification is the most well-known system (Das & Singh, 2016; Siyambalapitiya et al., 2018; Marshall, 2015).

An international growth in companies demanding situations and sustainability have compelled many groups across the world to carry in studies which might be pleasant and suitable for figuring out modern trending strategies to be available

for implementation in the direction of gaining a sustainable competitive marketplace. One of the main and most important strategies is green human resource management (GHRM) which concentrates on the framework of the friendly-environment organization. Research carried out by (Emmanuel et al., 2020) exhibited that majority of organizations are unsuccessful in a competitive environment while enterprise environments of those organizations are grasped for triviality.

In conclusion, there is a necessity of proactive green practices on the HRM department (Jabbour et al., 2010). Adoption of green practices in companies can result in better performance (Schuler & Jackson, 2014) improvement in organization culture (Jabbour et al., 2013) reduction of cost, effective utilization and improving company goodwill (Molina-Azorin et al., 2021). Therefore, a set of researches' view lead to the admission that establishing green human resource management (GHRM) is a worthy consideration. However, regarding to the research done by way of (Rani and Mishra, 2014), the write elaborated that, "Function of HR will be converted into primary motivator of sustainability inside in the companies by adjusting its standards, policies and practices with sustainability objectives imitating focus". With all that, this study is lay on to the new era of getting this strategy smart plan injected into the managerial systems. This study will address the effect of the GHRM Practices on the Turkish manufacturing and production industry and its sustainable and competitive edge.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies discusses the importance of greening, green business is one of those definitions that is supported in many of them. The abovementioned "genetic" connection between green business philosophy and sustainable development says why it is frequently comprehended- explicitly or implicitly – as being interchangeable with the topic of "sustainable business". A case in point, Brown and Ratledge state that green business is "an establishment that produces green output" (Ratledge & Brown, 2011). Meanwhile, The Business Dictionary indicates, "green business will engage further policies for environmental concerns affecting human rights". Similarly, "Definition of a "green business" is that a firm that utilizes renewable resources (environmentally sustainable) and keeps itself answerable for the human resources factor of their activities (socially responsible)" (Jeruto et al., 2017). Other authors emphasize about the "green behaviors" that the organizations should implement "green activities" under the badge of (GHRM) practices in order to produce the convenient green atmosphere. For instance, requirements upon the firm to unearth means to extinguish destructive discharges, produce and employ renewable energy, and reshape procedures and products for recycling (McClenahan & Milligan, 1998). Emerging to answer these questions will assist the firm function in Eco-friendly and net and clean way and turn into sustainable, increasing firm's competitive advantages. In this study, four components of the HRM practices will all gather inside the green circle, to investigate the effects between "going green" and the sustainable competitive edge in the manufacturing industry in Turkey. These are; green selection and recruitment, green training, green pay and rewards system, green involvement or in other words green employee relations/orientations. Trade is an essential component of economic development. However, it is not possible to conduct it in a sustainable way without responsible environmental management. For this reason, the concept of sustainability in international trade has come to the fore. How well the world economies are prepared to achieve sustainable growth through international trade is the determinant of success in today's growing competition (Uyan, 2021). Nowadays, an environmentally friendly sustainable trade and environmental management systems are especially important for manufacturing industries. Organizations need to benefit from the human factor at the highest level in order to reach their basic and strategic goals. For this reason, performance management is given great importance in today's businesses. Performance management is a process in which the performance evaluation system is integrated with other human resources systems, and performance is planned, evaluated and developed in order to harmonize employees' goals with organizational goals. Rewarding the employees in line with their performance increases the productivity and motivation of the employees and plays an important role in the success of the organization they are affiliated with (Günaydın & Uyan, 2019). In today's modern human resources management approach, the sensitivity of the employees to the environmental practices of the organization is also taken into consideration while evaluating the performance. Thus, it is possible for the organization to achieve its green management goals. As many researchers have studied the importance of the HRM practices, there was no combination between them and the environmental management. Nowadays, we can prove this relation by the writing of (Renwick et al., 2008); this amalgamation by "Green Human Resource Management" (GHRM) was brainstormed for the very first time, and instigated to add to the system of HRM research, more opportunities to integrate the definition of environmental focus. The green movement has leaded the community of industry and business to formulate green management by implementing environmentally friendly products and practices. Most of the definitions concluded by authors are almost the same except with some changes. For instance, it's emphasized that GHRM is explained as "using HRM practices with an aim to promote the sustainable utilization of resources which will strengthen the environmental sustainability in

general. (Opatha, & Arulrajah, 2014) elaborated GHRM via a procedure of turning workforce green for the gains of the society, individual, business and natural environment. Likewise, (Rana & Jain, 2014) comprehended the GHRM from the perspective of a model, which is elaborated as an employment model planned to help the professionals in the industry to in developing, preserving, recalling and retaining the proficiencies and capabilities to assure the strategies and initiatives for future businesses are met. Additionally, (Rani & Mishra, 2014) illustrated the GHRM as the ecological demeanor of industrial policies, monetary policies, and foreign policies as well, in order to reinforce the eco-system causing a disinfected environment. GHRM is the utilization of every worker touch point/interface to encourage enhanced employee conscious and sustainable practices and dedication on the problems of sustainability.

The Authors (Nayak & Mohanty, 2017) once defined the importance of greening the functional dimensions of HRM, which explains many activities like analysis and job description, selection, training, recruitment, rewards and performance appraisal is the reason of the GHRM. They came back (Nayak, Sahoo & Mohanty, 2018) to increase the study value by adding some competitive advantages to the term of GHRM practices. The term of GHRM is associated to the term of HRM operation as the driver of the organization to take up the green initiatives. The GHRM is an offshoot of the management philosophy, practices and policies, followed by a firm for environment management. As well, researchers assert that an enhanced performance in a firm would cause a decrease in employee carbon footprints by the means of GHRM practices like as job-sharing, teleconferencing, energy efficient office space, online training, telecommuting, recycling, virtual interviews, car-sharing, electronic filing, flexible work schedule etc. GHRM provides confidence the sustainable utilization of resources inside the business firm and promote the term of environmental sustainability, green HR is the sole reason of HR policies. On this paper, GHRM practices are being adapted as a reflection of the HR policies and the process of the going green to the general benefits of the environment management and the ongoing business competitiveness. These are remarked as recruitment practices, training and development practices, compensation structure, and employee empowerment. All that will be referred to the OPET incorporation branches in Turkey. GHRM are answerable to the green workplace qualifications, appreciate and maintain the green objectives under the expression of HR process through, recruitment, hiring, training, compensating and developing and advancing the firms of human capital (Mathapati, 2013).

The aim of the (GHRM) practices maintain in enhancing and retaining greening within the employees as the individual will work on having the highest contribution level needed at the organization (Ullah, 2017). As well as, it is debated that “workers must get environmentally empowered and conscious of the term of greening, in order to convey on the entire firm the management initiatives; utilizing reward programs and training systems, compensation and developments, enlistment and selection of employees, rigorous enlistment, appraisal system, employee relations and managerial support to attend to green movement (Sudin, 2011). Also he argued the positive impact of going green on the corporate environment citizenship, leading to the competitive advantage of the firms, which will be highlighted in the coming topics to explain what does sustainability mean, and what are the elements of this independent construct.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It has been claimed that involving the purpose of the study which includes the research objectives, research hypotheses and questions, with the data collection stage level subsequently pondering the ethical access and similar challenges (Thornhill et al., 2003), this opens an entrance through the necessity of defining what does research scheme mean. The research strategy is what it needs to be discovered and discussed by the researchers in order to have a set of answers to a set of questions (Goddard & Melville, 2004). Nevertheless, quantitative research has been used in this study because it suits up the business research and leads to assessing both, empirical studies, numerical measurements, and so on until the analysis chapter; where we can address the research questions (Zikmund et al., 2010).

In addition, the researcher can choose the type of the research depending on the purpose.

- Exploratory research: is entirely expedient when the exact of the study is ambiguous. Scholars keep on trying to understand ‘what is occurring; to search new findings and to wonder and to assess phenomena in a new spot light (Saunders et al., 2010).
- Descriptive research: is utilized to illustrate an exact profile of individual, event or situation. It is requisite to define the kind of the occurrence of your interest before you initiate the study data gathering process and goal. This type of research can be a forerunner to, a piece, an exploratory part or, sometimes, a part of explanatory research (Saunders et al., 2010).

- Explanatory research: emphasizes on studying a situation or a problem in order to explain the connection and the relationship between variables (Saunders et al., 2010)

Regarding descriptive study means to explain the study by opinions, beliefs and attitudes towards appropriate population (Memon et al., 2019; Raza and & Almashaqbeh, 2021). On this note, it has used this descriptive method to define the relationships between the sub-variables and to enclose the questionnaire answers with certain procedures. The work that will guide to the numerical data analysis and study conclusions, with supports by statistical variations composed of, means, standards deviations, and others. A primary source was used to collect the method from OPET incorporation in Turkey. A questionnaire will be distributed as a major evaluating instrument, which can be personally administer, sent through email or electronically administered for e.g. through an online Google forms for survey templates. The survey design will be informed by reviewing previews different studies, academic literatures and together with revision and modifications with local experts. Semi-structured questions were composed of both open and close-ended questions to address the issue of the study. Where the open-ended questions were designed to grab the unrecognized objectives in the options available for response in the socio-demographic section. However, the questionnaire will comprise three sections; the introduction, socio-demographic characteristics and the research questions.

4. RESEARCH ANALYSIS & DISCUSSIONS

In the research analysis descriptive statistics frequency tables generated in SPSS Software 26.0 version and all results are presented and interpreted as follows:

Gender:

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	169	67.6	67.6
Female	81	32.4	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 1 presents the frequency distribution of Gender of respondents working in OPET Corporation. The highest ratio is 67% of male employees working in OPET Corporation. While 33% were women. Women mostly work in the chemistry department for checking the chemicals of ultra-force and Eco force. While men work in outdoor activities such as OPET fuel stations.

Age:

Table 2: Age of Respondents

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
20-29 years	55	22.0	22.0
30-39 years	126	50.4	72.4
40-49 years	54	21.6	94.0
50 years & above	15	6.0	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 2 is presenting the age group of respondents here the highest age group working in OPET Corporation is between 30-39 years old. Half of the percentage (50.4%) comes from this age group. Because OPET believes in Youth and working for the betterment of youth under this age group. Employees are a bit experienced in work and organizations. The second high ratio is 20-29 years old almost (22%) of respondents are from this age group. Mostly they are new employees such as junior assistants, internees (completing their training for their degrees), entry-level and production assistants, marketing assistants, sales assistants, and finance assistants. 40-49 years this age group has the almost same percentage of respondents (21.6%) they all are senior employees working in the OPET Corporation. Having better experience, playing in the environments, and sincere with the OPET. Very few respondents almost (6%) are following in the range of 50-60 years old. They are the most sincere and obedient employees in OPET, also competing in the Turkish petrol and gas markets. That age group designations are CEO, CFO, CMO, and CPO.

Education:

Table 3: Education of Respondents

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Uneducated	14	5.6	5.6
University and beyond	154	61.6	67.2
High School	26	10.4	77.6
Primary School / Secondary School	32	12.8	90.4
Others, Please Specify	24	9.6	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 3 presents the education profile of respondents mostly the workers in OPET who have cleared Primary and secondary levels of education from Turkish government primary schools. Almost (61.6%) of respondents are from University and beyond, they are enrolled at Istanbul University, Bogacizi university, Yildiz technical university, and Istanbul Aydin University. Some respondents got their degrees in the engineering field from Turkish respective universities and joined the OPET Corporation. Secondly (12.8%) are getting their education from primary and secondary schools since the questionnaires were formed also in the Turkish language so it was easily understood by them. (10.4%) respondents are from high school. These people want to serve their families. They are middle-class people and they just earn and eat. (9.6%) respondents are pursuing their professional courses from various recognized institutes, such as; ISMEK. The last ratio (5.6%) of respondents are not educated, so that's why they just only work as labor in OPET fuel stations.

Working Experience of Staff:

Table 4: Working Experience of Respondents

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-4 years	84	33.6	33.6
5-9 years	54	21.6	55.2
10-14 years	70	28.0	83.2
15-19 years	30	12.0	95.2
20 years & above	12	4.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 4 presents the working experience profile of employees who are working in OPET Corporation in Turkey. The majority of workers are new almost (33.6%) of employees are working in OPET for 0-4 years. They are in the phase of learning trying to understand the OPET corporate culture and understanding the rules, regulations, and policies of OPET. The second high ratio is (28%) they are working in OPET between 10-14 years, and they are a bit senior in OPET. They understand all the internal and external matters of OPET Corporation. Thirdly (21.6%) employees working in OPET 5-9 years. They are familiar with the policies and corporate culture, infrastructure, and OPET environment. (12%) employees work with OPET for 15-19 years. They are well aware of OPET's competitors. They are making new strategies how to compete and beat the Turkish oil and gas markets. In the last OPET has also had very loyal employees, who work more than 20 years (4.8%). These employees present the OPET symbol and survive in this competitive edge.

Working Position of Staff:

Table 5: Working Position of Respondents

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Senior Staff	56	22.4	22.4
Management Staff	61	24.4	46.8
Junior Staff	68	27.2	74.0
Contract Staff	65	26.0	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 5 presents the working position of staff members working in OPET Corporation in Turkey. OPET has a wide range of employees. Mostly the study was conducted on junior staff 27.2%. They are newly graduated just working with OPET for not more than 4 years. Almost this study was conducted by those who have awareness of sustainability and green projects. Secondly, the Contract employee's 26% ratio is working in OPET on a contractual basis may be for a year or six months, OPET is currently hiring such employees who have newly entered the market with a better knowledge of green HR practices. Thirdly Management staff is 24.4%. They are working as managers, in the lower, middle, and upper levels of management in OPET. They are working as finance managers, marketing managers, human resources managers, production managers, and operation managers. In the last 22.4% are senior staff OPET is providing training about Green HRM to the HR managers and recruitment and selection teams. The senior staff was responding that in Turkey almost all corporations are working on CSR activities and Green projects. Whether in Finance, marketing, or human resources.

Does your company have a formal management system such as ISO 14001 (EMS or GMS)?

Table 6: EMS/GMS implementation results

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Currently exist	243	97.2	97.2
Unsure	7	2.8	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 6 presents the views of the EMS/ GMS implementation system. The question is about does the company have a formal management system like EMS/ GMS and ISO. ISO has so many types such as ISO 9001-9004. Nowadays companies moving towards ISO 14001 which relates to the environment. Companies are moving on green and environmental projects. OPET currently exists 97.2 % and implements the ISO 14001 and GMS/ EMS system. While 2.8% are unsure whether OPET has adopted this system or not. Since they are unaware of these activities because these respondents might be from lower departments.

Do you think that Human Resource Management has a direct involvement on Green program?

Table 7: Green Program results

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	250	100.0	100.0
Total	250	100.0	

Table 7 presents the results of question regarding that does HRM has direct involvement with the Green program. All respondents respond yes the HRM department has a direct connection with Green programs in the 21st century. Modern corporations are jumping towards green human resources projects. OPET is also one of them all employees of OPET also suggest that Yes 100% that HRM and green projects have a direct involvement.

Mean and Standard Deviation of Demographic Profiles:

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics results

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender	1.32	.469
Age	2.12	.816
Education	2.59	.091
How long have you been working in this corporation?	2.33	.194
How would you classify your work position in your organization?	2.57	.104
Does your company have a formal management system such as ISO 14001 (EMS or GMS)?	1.11	.661
Do you think that Human Resource Management has a direct involvement on Green program?	1.00	.000

Table 8 provides the overall descriptive statistics summary of the questionnaire. Mean and standard deviations are two major tools for central tendency and dispersion measurements. Age has the highest standard deviation of 0.816. Age data is more deviated, secondly, data has deviated of ISO, GMS, and EMS implementation 0.661, and Gender data is almost half distributed because this contains only two options male and female, 0.469 data deviates from a central point. Working

with OPET data deviated 0.194, work position data deviated 0.104, Education profiles of respondents data deviated only 0.091 and HRM has direct involvement with the green program since this question has two options yes or no and refers Table 8 it was suggested by all respondents that yes, so that means data does not deviate in this question. The highest mean in the demographic characteristics are Education 2.59. Secondly, the work position contains a 2.57 mean. Although central tendency has three measurements but here it only focused on a mean. Working with OPET has a 2.53 mean. The age means the value is 2.12. Gender is 1.32. Implementation of ISO has 1.11 and in the last, all values are 1 so their data is not disperse it is all at the central point. 1.00 yes HRM has a direct connection with green involvement.

Mean and Standard Deviation of Scales:

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of Scales results

	Mean	Std. Deviation
EPS	4.5944	.49751
GRS	4.4507	.52302
GTP	4.5253	.53568
GPRS	4.4747	.52813
PGI	4.4707	.54169

Table 9 has the same analysis as Table 9. This table presents the descriptive statistics summary of scales, such as GRS, GTP, GPRS, PGI, and EPS. Each scale contains some items. By computing, the mean point’s variables were computed in SPSS 27.0 version. After the creation of the variable again mean and standard deviation has calculated, and the highest mean has Employee perceived sustainability 4.59 data is more close to the central point and less depressed at 0.4975. The other variable green training practices have a 4.42 mean and 0.535 data is deviated since getting mostly the same results by the majority of respondents. Green recruitment and selection have the third-highest mean in the data at 4.45 and data is also dispersed by 0.523. While green pay and rewards and green involvement have approximately the same mean of 4.47 but the data of green involvement is more distributed 0.54 by green pay and reward. 0.528.

5. CONCLUSION

Previous studies suggest that human resources management is one of the major departments in every business organization, (Del Brío, 2007). But there is very small research carried out on Green human resources management. There is also no authentic measurement tool that measures the GHRM practices. (Renwick et al., 2013) suggests that there should be key elements and factors of green human resources management. (Zibarras and Coan, 2015) carried research on two major factors of GHRM. He tested a relationship between green recruitment and selection and green performance appraisal and suggested that new employees have created a positive image of the organization. If that organization follows a green process of recruitment and selection. (Guiyao et al., 2017) researched on GHRM taking five components; GRS, GTP, GPP, GI, and GPA. They proposed five hypotheses and gathered data from Chinese entrepreneurs. They also suggest that performance appraisal is the GPA that is a continuously ongoing process of measuring and checking the performance of the employees. Green Involvement is affecting positively in Palestine markets. (Marsi & Jaron, 2017) research in three sectors food, chemical, and pharm businesses in Palestine. They used both approaches of research qualitative (interviews from the HR department) and quantitative includes (Likert scales). (Marsi and Jaron, 2017) uses six independent variables GRS, GTP, GPR, GI, GPA, and GOC, all are positively affecting (P<0.05) employees’ perceived sustainability on environmental performance. Our study on Green Involvement is not effecting on employees’ perceived sustainability in the Turkish oil and gas sector since the (P>0.05). (Ullah, 2017) concluded in her research that GHRM factors are affecting employees socially and economically, especially in the oil and gas sector should work on sustainable projects, which are beneficial for employees. Due to climate change companies are adopting sustainability and green projects (Kodua et al., 2022) did research in Ghana on GHRM on economic performance and discovered five major obstacles faced by Ghanaian firms when they adopt the sustainable projects. Turkey has a good climate change, and OPET is formulating sustainable and CSR projects. (Arulrajah et al., 2015) makes descriptive study based on past literature and material, identified twelve major functions of Green human resources management organizations should be implemented. In OPET four functions are running, GRS, GTP, GPR, and GI. OPET should work on Green compensation plans, green job analysis, green job design, green induction, green HR planning, green employee relations, green safety, and green discipline. OPET has a strong organizational culture that conducts sustainable projects on social, economic, and environmental. OPET is located in Istanbul but it has sub-branches in Ankara and Izmir. (Fayyazi et al., 2015) worked on

the barriers in the oil and gas sector about green human resources management, his studies suggested in GHRM there are so many managerial, cultural and technological barriers. And his results by applying the Friedman test all suggested positive these barriers positively affected the GHRM.

Ethical Approval and Consent to participate:

Not applicable (I am only using numbers of medication requesting in the system without employees personal information or any record number also the survey conducted not involve any employee information) I am ensuring respect for all human subjects and protect their health and rights.

Availability of data and materials:

Data were collected from Oil and gas sector companies in Istanbul Turkey especially larger sample gathered from OPET Corporation using questionnaires via Google Forms <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeuHMGO5FnRzSzUashMVUCwQ8c9SKL1HYAS5Ssgw0-aHo4x0Q/viewform>. The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests:

The author declare that they have no competing interests

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Author contributions:

Mhd Sobhi AL SABI, conceived of the presented idea. Mhd Sobhi AL SABI developed the theory and performed the computations also verified the analytical methods. Mhd Sobhi AL SABI also discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

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